

ESTIMATION OF COPPER IN PRESENCE OF IRON

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For the analysis of copper ores containing iron, it was required to devise a convenient and quick method for the estimation of copper when potassium or ammonium flourides were not available. Cupric salts are usually determined iodometrically after precipitating Cu_2I_2 according to equation

Other radicals usually associated with copper ores such as iron arsenic and antimony interfere with the iodometric estimation of copper. Ferric iron is reduced by iodide,

but by addition of excess of potassium or ammonium flouride, the ferric iron is converted into complex (FeF_6)⁻³ which yields so small concentration of ferric ions in the solution that it has no oxidising action upon the iodide and thus it enables a quick quantitative estimation of copper in presence of iron (Fraser, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1915, 34 462). If iron were present in a copper solution in the ferrous state then according to equation (ii) it would not react with KI, but as the reaction is reversible, part of it would be oxidised by the iodine liberated by copper ions according to equation (i). In presence of excess of potassium iodide, however, as the free iodine liberated by copper is removed by thiosulphate, any ferric ion formed would react with excess of potassium iodide present and would liberate that amount of iodine which was used before in the process of oxidation of Fe^{++} to Fe^{+++} . At the end the amount of iodine liberated by copper ions would be determined quantitatively. As the reaction (ii) is reversible so it will take time. Based on these considerations, following experiments were carried out and then a method to estimate copper in the presence of iron was evolved.

Iron and arsenic, in consequence of the oxidising medium usually employed to bring the copper ore into solution, would be present in solution in tri- and quinquivalent states respectively. Therefore sets of mixtures containing varying amounts of copper sulphate, ferric chloride and sodium arsenate were prepared. The solutions were reduced by zinc amalgam and sulphuric acid (Clowes and Coleman, "Quantitative Analysis" 14th edition 193, 1688). When reduction was complete the free acid in the solution was, neutralised with sodium carbonate and then acetic acid and

potassium iodide solutions were added to each of the solutions to be titrated. Iodine liberated was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution using starch as indicator.

TABLE I.

A = 25% Acetic acid solution. B = 20% Potassium iodide solution.
Time taken for titration = 8-9 min.

No.	Vol of 2% CuSO ₄ , 5H ₂ O soln.	Vol. of 2% FeCl ₃ soln.	Vol of 2% Na arsenate soln.	3.5 c.c. A + 20 c.c. B Room temp.	Vol. of N/10 thio Calc.	Found.
1	20 c.c.	5 c.c.	5 c.c.	30 c.c. H ₂ O	16.06 c.c.	16.06 c.c.
2	20	10	10	20	"	16.06
3	20	15	15	10	"	16.08
4	20	20	20	0	"	16.08
5	0	20	20	20	0	0.0

Thus it is clear from Table I that by this method copper can be estimated accurately iodometrically in the presence of other ions such as Fe⁺⁺⁺ and As⁺⁺⁺⁺ which ordinarily interfere in this estimation.

Copper content of four samples of copper ores was then determined by the reduction method outlined above and the results were further checked by the fluoride method. It was found (Table II) that the results obtained were in excellent agreement.

TABLE II.

Amount of ore taken.	Copper found by		Error
	Reduction method	Fluoride method.	
0.5 g.	20.36%	20.36%	0.0%
1.0	20.33	20.40	-0.7
1.5	20.46	20.38	+0.08
2.0	20.43	20.43	+0.0